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READING COMPREHENSION SKILLS OF LEARNERS IN PRINT VERSUS DIGITAL READING MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effects of digital versus print reading materials on the reading comprehension of thirty Grade 8 learners at Dr. Catalino Gallego Nava Memorial High School, San Lorenzo, Guimaras, Philippines, during School Year 2025–2026. Using an experimental research design, the learners were divided into an experimental group exposed to interactive digital reading materials and a control group using traditional printed texts. A researcher-made test assessed learners' performance in pre-tests and post-tests, and data were analyzed using mean scores and t-tests. Findings revealed that both groups had comparable baseline comprehension, with no significant difference in pre-test scores, ensuring a balanced starting point for the intervention. Post-test results showed that learners using digital materials achieved higher mean scores and very satisfactory comprehension, while the printed materials group showed only slight improvement. Although the difference in post-test scores between the groups was not statistically significant, learners using digital materials demonstrated significant gains from pre-test to post-test, highlighting the effectiveness of guided digital reading interventions. The minimal improvement in the printed materials group suggests that traditional print alone may have limited impact without interactive or guided support. The study also indicates that digital reading materials may enhance engagement and motivation, which can contribute to better comprehension outcomes. These findings align with both foreign and local studies emphasizing the benefits of digital reading when combined with instructional guidance. Overall, both reading formats contributed to comprehension gains, but digital materials offered practical advantages, supporting their use as an effective tool for improving learners' reading comprehension skills.

Key words: Digital, Printed, Reading Materials, Effects, Grade 8 Learners

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